

**ROLE OF DOCTORAL SCHOOL IN
DIDACTIC AND ACADEMIC STAFF TRAINING
(Comparative Analysis: the Republic of Moldova and the
Republic of Maldives)**

**ROLUL ȘCOLII DOCTORALE ÎN FORMAREA PERSONALULUI
DIDACTIC ȘI ACADEMIC
(analiză comparativă: Republica Moldova și Republica Maldives)**

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Sumar. Acest articol reflectă rolul formativ al școlii doctorale în dezvoltarea profesională, științifică și didactică a viitoarelor cadre universitare. Pornind de la obiectivul identificării contribuției formării doctorale la integrarea absolvenților în învățământul superior, cercetarea urmărește cinci direcții principale: cadrul instituțional al școlii doctorale, competențele dobândite, mecanismele de îndrumare și coordonare, propunerile de inserție și optimizare profesională. Printr-o analiză comparativă între Republica Moldova și Republica Maldives, articolul evidențiază bune practici și provocări specifice, formulând recomandări concrete pentru creșterea eficienței programelor doctorale în raport cu nevoile actuale ale mediului academic.

Cuvinte-cheie: studii doctorale, învățământ superior, competențe academice, mentorat, carieră academică universitară, internaționalizare.

INTRODUCTION

In the current context of the development of knowledge society, higher education has an essential role in preparing qualified scientific and teaching staff, capable of responding to the increasingly complex requirements of an economy based on innovation, research and sustainable development. In this sense, the training of teaching and academic staff becomes a strategic priority, and the doctoral school represents a fundamental institutional framework in this process.

Doctoral school is not only a higher stage of academic training, but also a space for scientific, professional and personal development. Here, doctoral students accumulate

advanced knowledge in their field of research, and develop essential competences for an academic and teaching career: the ability to think critically, to develop and publish scientific papers, to deliver courses, and to lead research projects.

Given these considerations, we aim to establish the contribution of the doctoral school in the professional, scientific and didactic training of university education teaching staff, by highlighting the competences developed during PhD studies, the institutional mechanisms for coordinating research within doctoral studies, as well as the degree of preparation of graduates for integration into the academic environment, conducting a comparative analysis between the experiences of the Republic of Moldova and the Republic of Maldives, offering a contextualized perspective on the challenges and opportunities for the development of doctoral programs.

By addressing these directions, we aim to provide an image of how doctoral school contributes to shaping the future generation of university teaching staff and to identify good practices that can be replicated and adapted in various educational contexts.

INSTITUTIONAL AND FUNCTIONAL FRAMEWORK OF DOCTORAL SCHOOL

The doctoral school is a central component of the higher education system, with the mission of training highly qualified researchers and teaching staff. Within the university structure, it functions as a distinct academic unit, which coordinates the activity of doctoral training, establishing quality standards, selection criteria and continuous evaluation mechanisms.

At the institutional level, the legal and administrative framework of the doctoral school is regulated by national legislation in the field of education and research, supplemented by internal regulations adopted by universities. In the Republic of Moldova, the framework is established by the Education Code and regulated by Government decisions and orders of the Ministry of Education and Research [4; 5]. In the Republic of Maldives, the higher education system is more recently developed, but is based on international models, with British and Australian influences, with a flexible approach to the organization of doctoral studies [1; 3]. Functionally, the doctoral school is based on a series of key principles:

- *Academic autonomy*: ensures freedom of research and choice of topics in accordance with the scientific and professional needs of the doctoral student.
- *Quality of training*: implies the existence of clear criteria for admission, evaluation, thesis defense and continuous training.
- *Coordination*: each doctoral student is supported by one or more scientific advisors, whose role is to guide research and professional development activity.
- *Internationalization*: academic mobilities, participation in international conferences and interuniversity collaborations contribute to strengthening the professional profile of the doctoral student.

In the Republic of Moldova, doctoral schools are organized within universities with advanced research and education status, benefiting from public funding and, sometimes, international grants. There is a clear trend of reforming and modernizing doctoral programs, in line with the requirements of the European Higher Education Area (Bologna Process) [2].

In the Republic of Maldives, the doctoral system is still in its infancy, but it is characterized by a broad openness to international partnerships and adaptability. Due to the small number of higher education institutions (the National University of Maldives - the first and largest university in the country, offering various programs in fields such as health, education, engineering, tourism, law, arts, technology and medicine; the Islamic University of Maldives, a public university specializing in Islamic studies, law (Sharia), Arabic language and education), doctoral training is often carried out in collaboration with universities abroad, which brings benefits, but also challenges related to the integration of graduates into the local academic environment [3].

Therefore, the institutional and functional framework of the doctoral school directly influences the quality of the training process of academic staff. An efficiently organized doctoral school, with clear guidance and coordination policies, institutional support and international openness, contributes significantly to the development of an academic body, competitive, competent and adaptable to the challenges of the contemporary academic world.

Key Competences Developed During Doctoral Studies

Doctoral studies do not only involve deepening a research topic, but also constitute a period of intense development of professional and personal competences necessary for a successful academic career. Through the specific activities carried out – scientific research, writing articles, participating in conferences, assisted or independent teaching – the doctoral student goes through a complex process of forming a set of transferable competences, essential in the academic environment.

The most obvious dimension of the doctorate is research. During this stage, the future teacher or researcher develops the following competences:

- Formulation of research hypotheses and objectives;
- Establishment of research methodology and correct application of qualitative/quantitative scientific methods;
- Critical analysis of specialized literature and identification of scientific gaps;
- Elaboration of scientific papers and compliance with ethical norms in research;
- Dissemination of results in specialized publications or scientific presentations.

A significant proportion of PhD students are oriented towards a career in higher education, for what the development of teaching competences is essential. In many institutions, PhD students are involved in pedagogical activities under the guidance of permanent professors. This process contributes to the development of:

- skills in organizing and supporting courses, seminars and practical work;
- usage of modern teaching and assessment methods (including the application of digital tools);
- effective communication with students and adaptation to their diverse needs;
- management of the educational process and elaboration of own teaching materials.

Doctoral studies also stimulate the development of transversal competences, increasingly in demand in the academic and professional environment:

- *Critical and reflective thinking* – the ability to analyze, evaluate, and build solid arguments;
- *Teamwork and interdisciplinary collaboration* – participation in national and international research projects;
- *Scientific communication skills* – writing and presenting papers in formal contexts (conferences, symposia);
- *Project management* – planning and coordinating activities in an organized framework;
- *Ethics and academic integrity* – compliance with the norms of good conduct in research and teaching.

Referring to doctoral students from the Republic of Moldova and the Maldives, where international mobility is becoming a central component of doctoral programs, intercultural competences and adaptability to diverse educational systems are becoming a major competitive advantage. These experiences contribute to:

- expansion of professional and collaborative networks;
- knowledge of international good practices;
- understanding of differences in approaches to research and education globally.

Thus, doctoral studies offer a complex and diversified training framework, preparing doctoral students not only to become experts in a field, but also to meet the demands of a multidimensional academic career.

MECHANISMS OF GUIDANCE AND COORDINATION WITHIN DOCTORAL SCHOOL

The success of a doctoral school is not measured only by the number of theses completed, but especially by the quality of the training process and the professional integration of graduates into the academic environment. An essential role in this endeavor is played by institutional support mechanisms and scientific and professional coordination relationships. They contribute to guiding the doctoral student, building a coherent career and developing a solid academic identity.

Guidance and coordination are a fundamental pillar in the doctoral process. The scientific supervisor is more than a technical supervisor – he/she becomes a trainer and sometimes even a professional role model. Key responsibilities include:

- Support of the doctoral student in choosing a relevant and feasible research topic;

- Provision of constant feedback on research progress;
- Facilitating of access to scientific networks and research projects;
- Encouragement for publication of results and participation in academic events;
- Ensuring of an ethical and stimulating working climate.

The quality of the relationship scientific advisor-doctoral student directly influences the motivation, perseverance and performance of the doctoral student. In addition to the direct relationship with the scientific advisor, the support provided by the educational institution is essential for the success of the doctoral process. This support can take various forms:

- *Funding*: doctoral scholarships, research grants, funds for mobility and conference participation.
- *Infrastructure*: access to laboratories, electronic libraries, databases, specialized software.
- *Complementary training* : academic writing workshops, courses to develop pedagogical or digital skills.
- *Dedicated administrative services*: offices for doctoral students, academic counseling and logistical support.

In the Republic of Moldova, many universities have implemented support programs within doctoral schools, with the support of the European Union (through projects such as Erasmus+ or Horizon Europe) [2]. In the Republic of Maldives, there are international collaboration initiatives that compensate through institutional mobilities and partnerships [1; 3].

An important support mechanism is the integration of doctoral students into an active academic community, where they can collaborate, exchange ideas and receive feedback. Discussion forums, research groups, internal doctoral conferences or summer schools contribute to: reducing academic isolation; stimulating interdisciplinarity; building useful professional networks in the long term. Opening up to collaboration between doctoral students and teaching staff from different departments or universities stimulates internal and international mobility.

Therefore, the coordination and institutional support mechanisms within the doctoral school have a decisive impact on the professional path of the doctoral student. A solid academic infrastructure, combined with quality mentoring relationships, contributes to the formation of professionals prepared to successfully integrate into the academic and research environment.

PROFESSIONAL INSERTION OF PHD GRADUATES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

The completion of doctoral studies marks not only an academic milestone, but also a turning point in the professional career of young researchers. The process of professional insertion in higher education involves their integration into university structures

as academic assistants, lecturers, scientific researchers or even project leaders. The success of this process depends on several factors, including the training provided within the doctoral program, the institutional context and national policies regarding employment in academia.

Doctoral studies provide graduates with a solid body of knowledge and competences, but the essential question is whether these competences meet the concrete requirements of the higher education system.

In the Republic of Maldives, where the university system is expanding, the professional insertion of doctoral graduates is often straightforward, but formal pedagogical training is lacking in many cases. Universities collaborate with international institutions to fill this gap through internships and postdoctoral training.

Employment opportunities in higher education vary considerably depending on the national context and educational policies. In the Republic of Moldova, the academic market is relatively saturated in some fields (humanities, social sciences), but open in others (technology, IT, exact sciences). Recruitment is also influenced by factors such as:

- availability of academic positions;
- institutional promotion criteria (publications, teaching experience).

In the Republic of Maldives, being a young university system, the need for teaching staff is high, and doctoral graduates benefit from rapid employment opportunities, including in academic leadership positions.

A successful professional insertion involves not only occupying a position, but also active integration into an academic community. In this regard, the following are relevant:

- existence of postdoctoral programs to ensure the continuity of research and the accumulation of experience;
- participation in academic networks, research groups and conferences;
- access to guidance and continuous education even after completing doctoral studies.

In both analyzed countries, the development of such postdoctoral structures is still in its infancy. The Republic of Moldova has made progress in this regard through European funds [2], while the Republic of Maldives relies predominantly on international partnerships to support continuous professional development [1].

Therefore, the professional insertion of doctoral school graduates into higher education is a complex process, influenced by previous training, institutional context and employment policies. Although doctoral training provides a solid foundation, a better alignment between acquired competences and the real demands of the academic environment is needed, as well as more consistent support during the postdoctoral transition period.

The analysis of the institutional framework, developed competences, support mechanisms and the process of professional insertion of graduates highlights a series of

essential aspects that influence the efficiency of doctoral programs. In both the Republic of Moldova and the Republic of Maldives, the doctoral systems have strong points, but also common or specific challenges.

An academic career requires not only excellence in research, but also solid teaching competences. Thus, for effective insertion in the academic environment, the following would be necessary:

- introduction of certain compulsory modules of pedagogical and digital training for doctoral students;
- organization of supervised teaching internships, with feedback from coordinating teachers;
- periodic evaluation of teaching skills as part of the training course.

This measure is relevant in both analyzed systems, but is particularly necessary in the Republic of Maldives, where formal didactic training of doctoral students is almost non-existent.

To facilitate professional insertion, the following is necessary:

- creation of *institutionalized postdoctoral programs* that allow for the continuation of research and the accumulation of experience in teaching and university management;
- provision of *academic career counseling* and support for integration into research projects or international networks;
- giving of *priority to doctoral graduates* in filling vacant university positions, based on clear and transparent criteria.

The Republic of Moldova is implementing these activities, while the Republic of Maldives could integrate such solutions through external collaborations and flexible institutional policies.

The mentoring and coordination relationship remains a key factor in doctoral training. The following is recommended:

- development of a code of ethics and good practices guidance and coordination, applicable in all doctoral schools;
- establishment of guidance and coordination contracts that clearly defines the responsibilities of both parties;
- periodic evaluation of the quality of guidance and coordination process through feedback from doctoral students.

In the Republic of Moldova, there are regulations in this regard, based on which each university develops its own institutional documents for conducting doctoral studies [4]. The Republic of Maldives, although at an early stage of establishing doctoral schools, can adopt effective international models.

Both the Republic of Moldova and the Republic of Maldives benefit from international support for the development of higher education. The following is recommended:

- creation of doctoral programs in co-tutorship or with double degree;

- expansion of international mobilities for doctoral students and professors;
- involvement in international research consortia and exchange of good practices.

This global openness contributes not only to the quality of research, but also to preparation for an internationalized and competitive academic career.

For the doctoral studies to be relevant, it is necessary to better adapt to the current demands of the labor market and the university system. Thus, the following is recommended:

- updating of doctoral curricula according to developments in the scientific and educational fields;
- establishment of partnerships between universities and research institutions to broaden the employment prospects of doctoral students;
- monitoring of the graduates' professional career to evaluate the real impact of doctoral studies.

CONCLUSIONS

The doctoral school plays an essential role in training future teaching and academic staff, providing not only scientific experience, but also teaching and managerial competences. The comparative study between the Republic of Moldova and the Republic of Maldives reveals the need for a balance between excellence in research and practical training for the academic environment.

To strengthen this formative role, a systemic approach is needed, centered on the quality of guidance and coordination of doctoral studies, sustainable institutional support, adaptation to the real requirements of universities and openness to international collaboration. By respecting these conditions, doctoral programs can become catalysts of change in higher education and in society.

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